

NDAC/LO/025

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DYNAMICAL SMOOTHING:

Inclusion of Attitude Continuity Conditions in the Set Solution

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1. Feasibility of Dynamical Smoothing

Dynamical (or numerical) smoothing, DS, is achieved by introducing into the Set Solution an analytical representation of the attitude motion around the z axis. The model should span a time interval (T_{DS}) much longer than the frame period (T_4) and should depend on a vector of free parameters of dimension much less than T_{DS}/T_4 . These parameters are determined simultaneously with the abscissae and instrument parameters by performing the Set Solution.

In order to formalise the feasibility criterion, let $\omega_0(t)$ be the true motion of the telescope around z and $T = [t_1, t_2[$ a given time interval of length $\geq T_{DS}$. DS is feasible on T if one can determine *a priori* an analytical function $\omega(t; \underline{\lambda})$, $t \in T$, such that

$$\inf_{\underline{\lambda}} \sup_{t \in T} |\omega(t; \underline{\lambda}) - \omega_0(t)| \leq \epsilon \quad (1a)$$

and

$$\dim(\underline{\lambda}) \leq \kappa(t_2 - t_1)/T_4 \quad (1b)$$

Here, ϵ is a small angle (~ 10 mas) and κ a small fraction (~ 0.1) to be specified along with the minimum interval length T_{DS} . Dynamical smoothing is furthermore applicable to the mission as a whole if the union of such feasible intervals comprises at least a certain fraction of the total observing time. (Cf. Donati, "On Dynamical Smoothing", April 1983.)

Although the above criterion is in principle sufficient, it would be unwise to leave the form of the analytical function $\omega(t; \underline{\lambda})$ completely unspecified. Firstly, in order that the observation equations shall be

readily computable and solved without unnecessary iteration, the dependence on $\underline{\lambda}$ should be explicit and preferably linear, or at any rate easily linearised. Secondly, since the function is to be determined from phase measurements obtained at regular intervals (frames), it must be band-limited with negligible power above $1/(2T_4) \approx 0.2$ Hz. Thirdly, it should be general enough to allow significant deviations from any nominal or idealised models of spacecraft and perturbations.

These conditions actually constrain the choice of $\omega(t; \underline{\lambda})$ to simple basis functions such as trigonometric series (with fixed periods), polynomials, and splines (with fixed breakpoints). The first condition, for instance, practically precludes a strict dynamical model with $\underline{\lambda}$ representing the kinematic initial conditions and torque model parameters; the second condition prevents modelisation of jitter; and the third effectively implies an even stricter frequency limit of $\kappa/(2T_4) \sim 0.02$ Hz.

In our case, a piecewise polynomial representation by means of splines seems to be the obvious choice, since this has already been adopted for the on-ground attitude reconstitution (NDAC/LO/006, 014). This is particularly well suited for the case where discontinuities in the various derivatives of $\omega_o(t)$ are known to exist as a result of the attitude control and solar radiation pressure.

2. Superframes, Observation Equations, and Transition Equations

A spline of order N , defined on a sequence $\{t_j\}$ of knots or breakpoints, consists of pieces of polynomials, each of degree $N-1$ and defined on an interval $t_{j-1} \leq t < t_j$, and satisfying given continuity conditions at the breakpoints. The interval between two successive breakpoints shall be called a superframe. In the superframe $SF_j = [t_{j-1}, t_j[$ the spline is

$$\omega(t; \underline{\lambda}) = \lambda_{j0} + \lambda_{j1}(t - \bar{t}_j) + \lambda_{j2}(t - \bar{t}_j)^2 + \dots + \lambda_{j(N-1)}(t - \bar{t}_j)^{N-1} \quad (2)$$

where $\bar{t}_j$ is a reference time for superframe j , e.g. $\bar{t}_j = \frac{1}{2}(t_{j-1} + t_j)$. With $\underline{\lambda}_j = (\lambda_{j0} \ \lambda_{j1} \ \dots \ \lambda_{j(N-1)})'$ denoting the relevant sub-vector of $\underline{\lambda}$, the observation equations for star i in SF_j can be written in matrix form

$$\underline{L}_{ij} \Delta \underline{\lambda}_j + \underline{Y}_{ij} \Delta \underline{U}_i + \underline{G}_{ij} \Delta \underline{Y} + (\text{unit covariance noise}) = \underline{h}_{ij} \quad (3)$$

in which the dimensions are

$$\left. \begin{array}{cccc} \underline{L}_{ij}(m_{ij}, N) & \underline{Y}_{ij}(m_{ij}, 1) & \underline{G}_{ij}(m_{ij}, \text{NPAR}) & \underline{h}_{ij}(m_{ij}, 1) \\ \underline{\Delta\lambda}_j(N, 1) & \underline{\Delta u}_i(1, 1) & \underline{\Delta\gamma}(\text{NPAR}, 1) & \end{array} \right\} \quad (4)$$

$\underline{\Delta u}_i$ is the correction to the mean abscissa of object i ; $\underline{\Delta\gamma}$ is the correction to the NPAR-vector of instrument parameters. m_{ij} is the number of observations contained in SF_j of object no. i . [Usually $m_{ij} = 9$, since each star is observed in nine successive frames while traversing the FOV.]

In a more general context (especially for comparison with the PRS Solution) we may refer to $\underline{\lambda}_j$ as a local parameter (since it occurs only in a limited number of successive observations), to $\underline{u}_i$ as a nodal parameter (since it corresponds to a node in the connexion graph describing the sparse matrix structure of the normals), and to $\underline{\gamma}$ as a global parameter (since it occurs in every observation equation). The development below is applicable to any problem in which each observation involves exactly one parameter of each kind.

The continuity conditions connect successive superframes by imposing a certain degree of smoothness of $\omega(t, \underline{\lambda})$ at the interior breakpoints (i.e., excluding the endpoints of the DS interval). Ordinarily, a spline of order N is constructed to give maximum smoothness at all interior breakpoints, viz. by making the spline and its $N-2$ first derivatives strictly continuous, but allowing arbitrary jumps of the $(N-1)$:th derivative at the breakpoints. We shall use a slightly different form of continuity condition, allowing "controlled" jumps of all derivatives, compatible with a given covariance matrix. Such conditions can be written in normalised form as transition equations

$$\underline{U}_j \underline{\Delta\lambda}_j + \underline{V}_j \underline{\Delta\lambda}_{j+1} + (\text{unit covariance noise}) = \underline{0} \quad (5)$$

where $\underline{U}_j$ and $\underline{V}_j$ are of dimension (N, N) . [In principle they could be of variable dimension (k_j, N) , with $0 \leq k_j \leq N$; but this added complexity does not seem warranted by computational savings.] Note that the right-hand side of (5) is set to $\underline{0}$ because any *a priori* non-zero expectation of the discontinuities (e.g. thruster reaction) is already incorporated by the

attitude reconstitution; the expectation of $\underline{U}_j \Delta \lambda_j + \underline{V}_j \Delta \lambda_{j+1}$ is therefore zero when it comes to the Set Solution.

The transition equation can in principle be regarded as an *a priori* observation equation. It is incorporated into the normals exactly as an observation equation, i.e. by adding the left-hand sides premultiplied by their own transpose. From a practical viewpoint we must however distinguish between the two kinds of equations, since the elimination of the local vectors is obviously complicated by the connexions established by the transition equations. This is precisely the subject of this study. To start with I will however consider the formation of normals without including transition equations; it is then easier to see the degree of complication added by the latter.

3. Normals Without Transition Equations

Aiming at maximum generality, I shall subsequently refer to λ_j , u_i , and y as the local, nodal, and global vectors (or parameters). Their dimensions are, respectively, DL, DY, and DG, and their numbers NL, NY, and NG = 1. (There is, by definition, only one global vector.) The local index is $j = 1, 2, \dots, NL$ and the nodal index $i = 1, 2, \dots, NY$. Furthermore, I assume that there are DR columns on the right-hand side (rhs) of (3). (Normally, of course, DR = 1.) Instead of (4), the dimensions are then

$$\left. \begin{array}{cccc} \underline{L}_{ij} (m_{ij}, DL) & \underline{Y}_{ij} (m_{ij}, DY) & \underline{G}_{ij} (m_{ij}, DG) & \underline{h}_{ij} (m_{ij}, DR) \\ \underline{\Delta \lambda}_j (DL, DR) & \underline{\Delta u}_i (DY, DR) & \underline{\Delta y} (DG, DR) & \end{array} \right\} \quad (6)$$

A translation into the more familiar terms of the Set Solution and PRS Solution is found in Table 1.

The various submatrices of the normals are always obtained as (sums of) products of two matrices from the top row of (6). Since we are anyway running out of one-letter designations, the following notations will be used (dimensions are given to the right):

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \underline{LL}_{ij} = \underline{L}'_{ij} \underline{L}_{ij} \\ \underline{LL}_j = \sum_i \underline{LL}_{ij} \end{array} \right\} \quad (DL, DL) \quad (7a)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \underline{LY}_{ij} &= \left(\underline{0} \quad \underline{0} \quad \dots \quad \overset{\leftarrow i:\text{th position}}{\underline{L}'_{ij} \underline{Y}_{-ij}} \quad \dots \quad \underline{0} \right) \\
 \underline{LY}_j &= \sum_i \underline{LY}_{ij} = \left(\underline{L}'_{1j} \underline{Y}_{-1j} \quad \dots \quad \underline{L}'_{NYj} \underline{Y}_{-NYj} \right)
 \end{aligned}
 \left. \vphantom{\begin{aligned} \underline{LY}_{ij} \\ \underline{LY}_j \end{aligned}} \right\} \text{(DL, NY*DY)} \quad (7b)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \underline{LG}_{ij} &= \underline{L}'_{ij} \underline{G}_{-ij} \\
 \underline{LG}_j &= \sum_i \underline{LG}_{ij}
 \end{aligned}
 \left. \vphantom{\begin{aligned} \underline{LG}_{ij} \\ \underline{LG}_j \end{aligned}} \right\} \text{(DL, DG)} \quad (7c)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \underline{Lh}_{ij} &= \underline{L}'_{ij} \underline{h}_{-ij} \\
 \underline{Lh}_j &= \sum_i \underline{Lh}_{ij}
 \end{aligned}
 \left. \vphantom{\begin{aligned} \underline{Lh}_{ij} \\ \underline{Lh}_j \end{aligned}} \right\} \text{(DL, DR)} \quad (7d)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \underline{YY}_{ij} &= \text{diag}(\underline{0} \quad \dots \quad \underline{Y}'_{ij} \underline{Y}_{-ij} \quad \dots \quad \underline{0}) \\
 \underline{YY}_j &= \sum_i \underline{YY}_{ij} = \text{diag}(\underline{Y}'_{1j} \underline{Y}_{-1j} \quad \dots) \\
 \underline{YY} &= \sum_j \underline{YY}_j = \text{diag}(\sum_j \underline{Y}'_{1j} \underline{Y}_{-1j} \quad \dots)
 \end{aligned}
 \left. \vphantom{\begin{aligned} \underline{YY}_{ij} \\ \underline{YY}_j \\ \underline{YY} \end{aligned}} \right\} \text{(NY*DY, NY*DY)} \quad (7e)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \underline{YG}_{ij} &= \begin{pmatrix} \underline{0} \\ \vdots \\ \underline{Y}'_{ij} \underline{G}_{-ij} \leftarrow i:\text{th position} \\ \vdots \\ \underline{0} \end{pmatrix} \\
 \underline{YG}_j &= \sum_i \underline{YG}_{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} \underline{Y}'_{1j} \underline{G}_{-1j} \\ \vdots \\ \underline{Y}'_{NYj} \underline{G}_{-NYj} \end{pmatrix} \\
 \underline{YG} &= \sum_j \underline{YG}_j = \begin{pmatrix} \sum_j \underline{Y}'_{1j} \underline{G}_{-1j} \\ \vdots \end{pmatrix}
 \end{aligned}
 \left. \vphantom{\begin{aligned} \underline{YG}_{ij} \\ \underline{YG}_j \\ \underline{YG} \end{aligned}} \right\} \text{(NY*DY, DG)} \quad (7f)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \underline{Y}_{ij} &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \vdots \\ \underline{Y}'_{ij} h_{ij} \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \leftarrow i\text{:th position} \\
 \underline{Y}_j &= \sum_i \underline{Y}_{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} \underline{Y}'_{1j} h_{1j} \\ \vdots \\ \underline{Y}'_{-NYj} h_{-NYj} \end{pmatrix} \\
 \underline{Y} &= \sum_j \underline{Y}_j = \begin{pmatrix} \sum_j \underline{Y}'_{1j} h_{1j} \\ \vdots \end{pmatrix}
 \end{aligned}
 \left. \vphantom{\begin{aligned} \underline{Y}_{ij} \\ \underline{Y}_j \\ \underline{Y} \end{aligned}} \right\} \text{(NY*DY, DR)} \tag{7g}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \underline{GG}_{ij} &= \underline{G}'_{ij} \underline{G}_{ij} \\
 \underline{GG}_j &= \sum_i \underline{GG}_{ij} \\
 \underline{GG} &= \sum_j \underline{GG}_j
 \end{aligned}
 \left. \vphantom{\begin{aligned} \underline{GG}_{ij} \\ \underline{GG}_j \\ \underline{GG} \end{aligned}} \right\} \text{(DG, DG)} \tag{7h}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \underline{Gh}_{ij} &= \underline{G}'_{ij} h_{ij} \\
 \underline{Gh}_j &= \sum_i \underline{Gh}_{ij} \\
 \underline{Gh} &= \sum_j \underline{Gh}_j
 \end{aligned}
 \left. \vphantom{\begin{aligned} \underline{Gh}_{ij} \\ \underline{Gh}_j \\ \underline{Gh} \end{aligned}} \right\} \text{(DG, DR)} \tag{7i}$$

$$\underline{\Delta u} = \begin{pmatrix} \underline{\Delta u}_1 \\ \underline{\Delta u}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \underline{\Delta u}_{NY} \end{pmatrix} \text{(NY*DY, DR)} \tag{7j}$$

TABLE 1. Translation of the general designations into those of the Set Solution and PRS Solution

GENERAL DESIGNATION (dimension, number)	SET SOLUTION ('geometric')	SET SOLUTION (here; DS)	PRS SOLUTION ('old' method)	PRS SOLUTION (NDAC/LO/021)
local vector $\underline{\lambda}_j$ (DL, NL)	frame attitude $\overline{\Delta\omega}$ (1, NFRAME*)	spline coeff $\underline{\lambda}_j$ (N, NSF*)	set zero point c_j (1, NSET)	astrom param $\underline{a}_i$ (NASPAR, NPRS)
nodal vector $\underline{v}_i$ (DY, NY)	abscissa v_i (1, NABSC*)	abscissa v_i (1, NABSC*)	astrom parameters (NASPAR, NPRS)	set orientation param $\underline{b}_j$ (NSETOR, NSET)
global vector $\underline{\gamma}$ (DG, NG)	instrum param $\underline{g}, \underline{h}$ (NPAR, 1)	instrum param $\underline{\gamma}$ (NPAR, 1)	system distortion (NGLOB, 1)	system distortion $\underline{g}$ (NGLOB, 1)

* NFRAME = number of frames in a set

NABSC = number of abscissae in a set

NSF = number of superframes in a set

The complete normals can now be written [cf (021.16)]

$$\begin{array}{cccccc}
 \underline{\Delta\lambda}_1 & \underline{\Delta\lambda}_2 & \dots & \underline{\Delta\lambda}_{NL} & \underline{\Delta u} & \underline{\Delta y} & \text{rhs} \\
 \hline
 \left(\begin{array}{cccccc}
 \underline{LL}_1 & & & & \underline{LY}_1 & \underline{LG}_1 & \underline{Lh}_1 \\
 & \underline{LL}_2 & \underline{0} & & \underline{LY}_2 & \underline{LG}_2 & \underline{Lh}_2 \\
 & \underline{0} & \ddots & & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\
 & & & \underline{LL}_{NL} & \underline{LY}_{NL} & \underline{LG}_{NL} & \underline{Lh}_{NL} \\
 \underline{LY}'_1 & \underline{LY}'_2 & \dots & \underline{LY}'_{NL} & \underline{YY} & \underline{YG} & \underline{Yh} \\
 \underline{LG}'_1 & \underline{LG}'_2 & \dots & \underline{LG}'_{NL} & \underline{YG}' & \underline{GG} & \underline{Gh}
 \end{array} \right)
 \end{array} \quad (8)$$

where, for compactness, the unknowns have been written on top of respective columns. The important feature here is the block-diagonal structure of the upper-left (NL*DL,NL*DL)-matrix. Assuming that each $\underline{LL}_j$ is positive definite, we can solve for $\underline{\Delta\lambda}_j$ in terms of $\underline{\Delta u}$ and $\underline{\Delta y}$, using the j:th row of (8):

$$\underline{\Delta\lambda}_j = \underline{LL}_j^{-1} \underline{Lh}_j - \underline{LL}_j^{-1} (\underline{LY}_j \quad \underline{LG}_j) \begin{pmatrix} \underline{\Delta u} \\ \underline{\Delta y} \end{pmatrix}, \quad j = 1 \text{ to } NL \quad (9)$$

Inserting these into the remaining equations,

$$\sum_j (\underline{LY}_j \quad \underline{LG}_j)' \underline{\Delta\lambda}_j + \begin{pmatrix} \underline{YY} & \underline{YG} \\ \underline{YG}' & \underline{GG} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \underline{\Delta u} \\ \underline{\Delta y} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \underline{Yh} \\ \underline{Gh} \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

we get the following system of normals for $\underline{\Delta u}$ and $\underline{\Delta y}$ only:

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 \underline{\Delta u} & \underline{\Delta y} & \text{rhs} \\
 \hline
 \left(\begin{array}{ccc}
 \underline{YY} - \sum_j \underline{LY}'_j \underline{LL}_j^{-1} \underline{LY}_j & \underline{YG} - \sum_j \underline{LY}'_j \underline{LL}_j^{-1} \underline{LG}_j & \underline{Yh} - \sum_j \underline{LY}'_j \underline{LL}_j^{-1} \underline{Lh}_j \\
 \text{(symmetric)} & \underline{GG} - \sum_j \underline{LG}'_j \underline{LL}_j^{-1} \underline{LG}_j & \underline{Gh} - \sum_j \underline{LG}'_j \underline{LL}_j^{-1} \underline{Lh}_j
 \end{array} \right)
 \end{array} \quad (11)$$

This system, being of reasonable dimension (NY*DY+DG, NY*DY+DG+DR), can be solved by direct application of the Cholesky algorithm, using some suitable sparse matrix storage scheme (Section 5).

We shall now concentrate on the accumulation of the system (11). Since $\underline{LL}_j$ is positive definite it can be factorized (according to Cholesky) as

$$\underline{LL}_j = \underline{\tilde{L}}_j \underline{\tilde{L}}_j^T \quad (12)$$

with $\underline{\tilde{L}}_j$ an upper-diagonal (DL,DL)-matrix. Then

$$\underline{LL}_j^{-1} = \underline{\tilde{L}}_j^{-1} \underline{\tilde{L}}_j^{-T} \quad (13)$$

Performing the factorization $\underline{LL}_j \rightarrow \underline{\tilde{L}}_j$ is seen to be equivalent to pre-multiplication by $\underline{\tilde{L}}_j^{-T}$. Having done the factorization, it is a simple and explicit process to pre-multiplying any matrix $\underline{A}$ (with DL rows) by the same factor. This operation is indicated by a tilde; thus the notation

$$(\underline{LL}_j \quad \underline{A}) \xrightarrow{\text{Chol}} (\underline{\tilde{L}}_j \quad \underline{\tilde{A}}) \quad (14)$$

means simply

$$\underline{\tilde{L}}_j := (\text{Cholesky factor of } \underline{LL}_j), \quad \underline{\tilde{A}} := \underline{\tilde{L}}_j^{-T} \underline{A} \quad (15)$$

For any two matrices $\underline{A}$, $\underline{B}$ with DL rows we have

$$\underline{A}' \underline{LL}_j^{-1} \underline{B} = \underline{A}' \underline{\tilde{L}}_j^{-1} \underline{\tilde{L}}_j^{-T} \underline{B} = (\underline{\tilde{L}}_j^{-T} \underline{A})' (\underline{\tilde{L}}_j^{-T} \underline{B}) = \underline{\tilde{A}}' \underline{\tilde{B}} \quad (16)$$

Thus, after the transformation

$$(\underline{LL}_j \quad \underline{LY}_j \quad \underline{LG}_j \quad \underline{Lh}_j) \xrightarrow{\text{Chol}} (\underline{\tilde{L}}_j \quad \underline{\tilde{Y}}_j \quad \underline{\tilde{G}}_j \quad \underline{\tilde{h}}_j) \quad (17)$$

we obtain (11) more compactly as

$$\Sigma_j \begin{pmatrix} \underline{YY}_j - \underline{\tilde{Y}}_j' \underline{\tilde{Y}}_j & \underline{YG}_j - \underline{\tilde{Y}}_j' \underline{\tilde{G}}_j & \underline{Yh}_j - \underline{\tilde{Y}}_j' \underline{\tilde{h}}_j \\ \text{(symmetric)} & \underline{GG}_j - \underline{\tilde{G}}_j' \underline{\tilde{G}}_j & \underline{Gh}_j - \underline{\tilde{G}}_j' \underline{\tilde{h}}_j \\ & & \end{pmatrix} \quad (18)$$

The basic algorithm therefore consists in performing, for each j successively, the two steps (17) [Cholesky reduction of j :th line of (8)] and (18) [accumulation of normals]. To elaborate the algorithm further, we note that $\tilde{\underline{G}}_j$ and $\tilde{\underline{h}}_j$ are full matrices of very small dimensions, while $\tilde{\underline{Y}}_j$ contains $NL*DY$ columns [see (7b)] and is usually sparse, since $\tilde{\underline{Y}}_{ij} = \underline{0}$ except if the node i is observed in locus j . Writing $\tilde{\underline{Y}}_j$ as a sum over i as in (7b), we get

$$\Sigma_j \left\{ \begin{array}{ccc} \Sigma_i [\underline{Y}\underline{Y}_{ij} - \tilde{\underline{Y}}_{ij}' \Sigma_i \tilde{\underline{Y}}_{ij}] & \Sigma_i [\underline{Y}\underline{G}_{ij} - \tilde{\underline{Y}}_{ij}' \tilde{\underline{G}}_j] & \Sigma_i [\underline{y}\underline{h}_{ij} - \tilde{\underline{Y}}_{ij}' \tilde{\underline{h}}_j] \\ \text{(symmetric)} & \underline{G}\underline{G}_j - \tilde{\underline{G}}_j' \tilde{\underline{G}}_j & \underline{G}\underline{h}_j - \tilde{\underline{G}}_j' \tilde{\underline{h}}_j \end{array} \right\} \quad (19)$$

$$=: \left(\begin{array}{ccc} \underline{D} & \underline{E} & \underline{e} \\ \underline{E}' & \underline{F} & \underline{f} \end{array} \right)$$

Note that the term $-\tilde{\underline{Y}}_{ij}' \tilde{\underline{Y}}_{ij}$ adds $-(\underline{L}'_{ij} \underline{Y}_{ij})' (\underline{L}'_{ij} \underline{Y}_{ij})$ to the (i,i) :th sub-matrix of $\underline{D}$ [i.e. to $\underline{D}_{i1}$]. Since only the upper-diagonal part of the symmetric $\underline{D}$ is stored, the sum over i need only be taken for $i \geq i$. In fact we prefer to reverse the order of summation, so that

$$\underline{D} = \Sigma_j \Sigma_i [\underline{Y}\underline{Y}_{ij} - \Sigma_{i < j} \tilde{\underline{Y}}_{ij}' \tilde{\underline{Y}}_{ij}] \quad (20)$$

As mentioned in NDAC/LO/022 (Definition of Back-Substitution) we can avoid back-solving the local vectors after the last iteration of the normals by preadjusting them according to

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \Delta \underline{\lambda}_j := \underline{L}\underline{L}_j^{-1} \underline{L}\underline{h}_j \\ \underline{\lambda}_j := \underline{\lambda}_j + \Delta \underline{\lambda}_j \end{array} \right\} \quad (21)$$

With respect to these preadjusted vectors we clearly have $\underline{L}\underline{h}_j = \underline{0}$ and hence $\tilde{\underline{h}}_j = \underline{0}$, thus simplifying the last column of (19). Combining (17), (19), (20), and (21) we find the accumulation algorithm of Table 2. This is in all essentials identical to the one in Table 1 of NDAC/LO/022.

TABLE 2. Accumulation of normals without transition equations

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zero all  $\underline{D}_{-1i}$ ,  $\underline{E}_i$ ,  $\underline{e}_i$ , and  $\underline{F}$ ,  $\underline{f}$ 
loop through locals j
  ( $\underline{P}$   $\underline{R}$   $\underline{s}$ ) :=  $\underline{0}$ (DL, DL+DG+DR)
  loop through nodes i
    compute observation equation ( $\underline{L}_{-ij}$   $\underline{Y}_{-ij}$   $\underline{G}_{-ij}$   $\underline{h}_{-ij}$ )
     $\underline{H}_{-i} := \underline{L}_{-ij}' \underline{Y}_{-ij}$ 
    ( $\underline{P}$   $\underline{R}$   $\underline{s}$ ) := ( $\underline{P}$   $\underline{R}$   $\underline{s}$ ) +  $\underline{L}_{-ij}'$  ( $\underline{L}_{-ij}$   $\underline{G}_{-ij}$   $\underline{h}_{-ij}$ )
  next i
  if ( $\underline{P} > \underline{0}$ ) then
    ( $\underline{P}$   $\underline{R}$   $\underline{s}$ )  $\xrightarrow{\text{Chol}}$  ( $\tilde{\underline{P}}$   $\tilde{\underline{R}}$   $\tilde{\underline{s}}$ )
    preadjustment of local vector:  $\underline{\lambda}_j := \underline{\lambda}_j + \tilde{\underline{P}}^{-1} \tilde{\underline{s}}$ 
    loop through nodes i
       $\tilde{\underline{H}}_{-i} := \tilde{\underline{P}}^{-T} \underline{H}_{-i}$  (Cholesky reduction)
      loop through previous nodes  $1 < i$ 
         $\underline{D}_{-1i} := \underline{D}_{-1i} - \tilde{\underline{H}}_{-i}' \tilde{\underline{H}}_{-i}$ 
      next i
      ( $\underline{D}_{-ii}$   $\underline{E}_i$   $\underline{e}_i$ ) := ( $\underline{D}_{-ii}$   $\underline{E}_i$   $\underline{e}_i$ ) +  $\underline{Y}_{-ij}'$  ( $\underline{Y}_{-ij}$   $\underline{G}_{-ij}$   $\underline{h}_{-ij}$ ) -
         $\tilde{\underline{H}}_{-i}'$  ( $\tilde{\underline{H}}_{-i}$   $\tilde{\underline{R}}$   $\underline{0}$ )
      ( $\underline{F}$   $\underline{f}$ ) := ( $\underline{F}$   $\underline{f}$ ) +  $\underline{G}_{-ij}'$  ( $\underline{G}_{-ij}$   $\underline{h}_{-ij}$ )
    next i
     $\underline{F} := \underline{F} - \tilde{\underline{R}}' \tilde{\underline{R}}$ 
  endif
next j

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N.B.: $\underline{P} = \underline{L}\underline{L}'_j$, $\underline{R} = \underline{L}\underline{G}'_j$, $\underline{s} = \underline{L}\underline{h}_j$, $\underline{H}_{-i} = \underline{L}'_{-ij}\underline{H}_{-ij}$

4. Inclusion of Transition Equations

The transition equations involving a given local vector $\underline{\Delta\lambda}_j$ are

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \underline{U}_{j-1} \underline{\Delta\lambda}_{j-1} + \underline{V}_{j-1} \underline{\Delta\lambda}_j &= \underline{0} \\ \underline{U}_j \underline{\Delta\lambda}_j + \underline{V}_j \underline{\Delta\lambda}_{j+1} &= \underline{0} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (22)$$

The equations to be added to the normals (8) are therefore

$$\underline{V}'_{j-1} \underline{U}_{j-1} \underline{\Delta\lambda}_{j-1} + (\underline{V}'_{j-1} \underline{V}_{j-1} + \underline{U}'_j \underline{U}_j) \underline{\Delta\lambda}_j + \underline{U}'_j \underline{V}_j \underline{\Delta\lambda}_{j+1} = \underline{0}, \quad j = 1 \text{ to } NL \quad (23)$$

(we may assume that $\underline{U}_0 = \underline{V}_{NL} = \underline{0}$).

Clearly the upper-left (NL*DL, NL*DL)-matrix of the complete normals is no longer block-diagonal, as in (8), but block-tridiagonal:

$$\left(\begin{array}{ccccc} \underline{L}_1 + \underline{U}'_1 \underline{U}_1 & \underline{U}'_1 \underline{V}_1 & \underline{0} & \dots & \underline{0} \\ \underline{V}'_1 \underline{U}_1 & \underline{L}_2 + \underline{V}'_1 \underline{V}_1 + \underline{U}'_2 \underline{U}_2 & \underline{U}'_2 \underline{V}_2 & \dots & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \underline{V}'_2 \underline{U}_2 & \underline{L}_3 + \underline{V}'_2 \underline{V}_2 + \underline{U}'_3 \underline{U}_3 & \dots & \underline{0} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \underline{0} & \underline{0} & \underline{0} & \dots & \underline{L}_{NL} + \underline{V}'_{NL-1} \underline{V}_{NL-1} \end{array} \right)$$

$$=: \left(\begin{array}{ccccccc} \underline{P}_1 & \underline{Q}_1 & & & & & \\ \underline{Q}'_1 & \underline{P}_2 & \underline{Q}_2 & & & & \underline{0} \\ & \underline{Q}'_2 & \underline{P}_3 & \underline{Q}_3 & & & \\ & & \dots & \dots & \dots & & \\ & & & \dots & \dots & \dots & \\ \underline{0} & & & \underline{Q}'_{NL-2} & \underline{P}_{NL-1} & \underline{Q}_{NL-1} & \\ & & & \underline{Q}'_{NL-1} & \underline{P}_{NL} & & \end{array} \right) =: \underline{PQ} \quad (24)$$

Using contracted notations, the normals corresponding to (8) can be written [cf (021.16⁻)]

$$\begin{pmatrix} \underline{PQ} & \underline{LY} & \underline{LG} & \underline{Lh} \\ \underline{LY}' & \underline{YY} & \underline{YG} & \underline{Yh} \\ \underline{LG}' & \underline{YG}' & \underline{GG} & \underline{Gh} \end{pmatrix} \quad (25)$$

with $\underline{PQ}$ replacing $\underline{LL}$ in (8). Elimination of $\Delta\lambda$ yields a system analogous with (11) [cf (021.19')-(20')]:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \underline{YY} - \underline{LY}'\underline{PQ}^{-1}\underline{LY} & \underline{YG} - \underline{LY}'\underline{PQ}^{-1}\underline{LG} & \underline{Yh} - \underline{LY}'\underline{PQ}^{-1}\underline{Lh} \\ (\text{symmetric}) & \underline{GG} - \underline{LG}'\underline{PQ}^{-1}\underline{LG} & \underline{Gh} - \underline{LG}'\underline{PQ}^{-1}\underline{Lh} \end{pmatrix} \quad (26)$$

Now let $\underline{CK}$ be the Cholesky factor of $\underline{PQ}$, i.e. the upper-triangular matrix satisfying

$$\underline{CK}'\underline{CK} = \underline{PQ} \quad (27)$$

and let $\tilde{\sim}$ signify premultiplication by $\underline{CK}^{-T}$:

$$(\tilde{\underline{LY}} \quad \tilde{\underline{LG}} \quad \tilde{\underline{Lh}}) := \underline{CK}^{-T}(\underline{LY} \quad \underline{LG} \quad \underline{Lh}) \quad (28)$$

The normals analogous with (18) are then as follows:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \underline{YY} - \tilde{\underline{LY}}'\tilde{\underline{LY}} & \underline{YG} - \tilde{\underline{LY}}'\tilde{\underline{LG}} & \underline{Yh} - \tilde{\underline{LY}}'\tilde{\underline{Lh}} \\ (\text{symmetric}) & \underline{GG} - \tilde{\underline{LG}}'\tilde{\underline{LG}} & \underline{Gh} - \tilde{\underline{LG}}'\tilde{\underline{Lh}} \end{pmatrix} \quad (29)$$

The block-diagonal structure of $\underline{LL}$ made it possible to process each locus (j) independently of the others by the accumulation algorithm (Table 2). This is not possible in the case with transition equations, since these link together adjacent loci as indicated by the presence of off-diagonal submatrices ($\underline{Q}_j$) in (24). It is however still possible to perform the accumulation in a similar manner, with only one additional run through the loci in each direction (forward loop to compute $\underline{CK}$ etc, and a backward loop to preadjust the local vectors). The required recursions are as follows.

The Cholesky factor $\underline{CK}$ is upper-triangular and bounded by the same envelope (profile) as the matrix $\underline{PQ}$. Its structure is, consequently,

$$\underline{CK} = \begin{pmatrix} \underline{C}_1 & \underline{K}_1 & & & \underline{0} \\ & \underline{C}_2 & \underline{K}_2 & & \\ & & \cdot & \cdot & \\ & & & \cdot & \\ \underline{0} & & & & \underline{C}_{NL-1} & \underline{K}_{NL-1} \\ & & & & & \underline{C}_{NL} \end{pmatrix} \quad (30)$$

with all $\underline{C}_j$ upper-triangular. Inserting (30) and (24) in (27) we get

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \underline{C}_1' \underline{C}_1 &= \underline{P}_1, & \underline{C}_1' \underline{K}_1 &= \underline{Q}_1 \\ \underline{C}_2' \underline{C}_2 + \underline{K}_1' \underline{K}_1 &= \underline{P}_2, & \underline{C}_2' \underline{K}_2 &= \underline{Q}_2 \\ \vdots & & \vdots & \\ \underline{C}_{NL}' \underline{C}_{NL} + \underline{K}_{NL-1}' \underline{K}_{NL-1} &= \underline{P}_{NL}, & -- & \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (31)$$

from which we obtain recursively

$$\left. \begin{aligned} (\underline{C}_1 \quad \underline{K}_1) &= \underline{C}_1^{-T} (\underline{P}_1 \quad \underline{Q}_1) \\ (\underline{C}_2 \quad \underline{K}_2) &= \underline{C}_2^{-T} (\underline{P}_2 - \underline{K}_1' \underline{K}_1 \quad \underline{Q}_2) \\ \vdots & \\ (\underline{C}_{NL} \quad) &= \underline{C}_{NL}^{-T} (\underline{P}_{NL} - \underline{K}_{NL-1}' \underline{K}_{NL-1} \quad) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (32)$$

For an arbitrary matrix $\underline{A}$ with $NL * DL$ rows, $\underline{\tilde{A}} = \underline{CK}^{-T} \underline{A}$ is obtained by analogous recursions. The operation

$$(\underline{PQ} \quad \underline{A}) \xrightarrow{\text{Chol}} (\underline{CK} \quad \underline{\tilde{A}}) := \underline{CK}^{-T} (\underline{PQ} \quad \underline{A}) \quad (33)$$

is thus performed by the following algorithm:

loop through locals $j = 1$ to NL

$$\begin{aligned} \text{if } (j > 1) \text{ then } (\underline{P}_j \quad \underline{A}_j) &:= (\underline{P}_j \quad \underline{A}_j) - \underline{K}'_{j-1} (\underline{K}_{j-1} \quad \underline{\tilde{A}}_{j-1}) \\ (\underline{P}_j \quad \underline{Q}_j \quad \underline{A}_j) &\xrightarrow{\text{Chol}} (\underline{C}_j \quad \underline{K}_j \quad \underline{\tilde{A}}_j) \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

next j

In a similar way we find that the back-solving, i.e. computing

$$\underline{B} = \underline{C}\underline{K}^{-1}\underline{\tilde{A}} \quad [= \underline{P}\underline{Q}^{-1}\underline{A}] \quad (35)$$

is accomplished by the backwards recursion:

loop through locals $j = NL$ to 1 step -1

$$\begin{aligned} \text{if } (j < NL) \text{ then } \underline{\tilde{A}}_j &:= \underline{\tilde{A}}_j - \underline{K}_j \underline{B}_{j+1} \\ \underline{B}_j &:= \underline{C}_j^{-1} \underline{\tilde{A}}_j \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

next j

The resulting algorithm appears in Table 3. Comparing with Table 2 (no transition equations), it is seen that all essential differences lie in the portions of Table 3 labelled (i) to (iv). In fact, if these portions are deleted, the remaining algorithm is exactly equivalent to the one in Table 2, albeit the operations are not always performed in the same order.

This points at a simple way to generalise the accumulation algorithm to allow transition equations (connexions) at arbitrary breakpoints. Let $\text{connx}(j)$ be a logical array defined for $j = 0$ to NL in such a way that

$$\text{connx}(j) = \begin{cases} \text{true} & \text{if a connexion exists between loci } j \text{ and } j+1 \\ \text{false} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (37)$$

TABLE 3. Accumulation of normals including transition equations

zero all $\underline{D}_{-1i}$, $\underline{E}_{-i}$, $\underline{e}_{-i}$, and $\underline{F}$, $\underline{f}$

loop through locals $j = 1$ to NL

$(\underline{P}_j \quad \underline{R}_j \quad \underline{s}_j) := \underline{Q}(\underline{DL}, \underline{DL} + \underline{DG} + \underline{DR})$

loop through nodes i

compute observation equation $(\underline{L}_{-ij} \quad \underline{Y}_{-ij} \quad \underline{G}_{-ij} \quad \underline{h}_{-ij})$

$\underline{H}_{-ij} := \underline{L}_{-ij}' \underline{Y}_{-ij} \quad (= i\text{:th position in sparse matrix } \underline{H}_j)$

$(\underline{P}_j \quad \underline{R}_j \quad \underline{s}_j) := (\underline{P}_j \quad \underline{R}_j \quad \underline{s}_j) + \underline{L}_{-ij}' (\underline{L}_{-ij} \quad \underline{G}_{-ij} \quad \underline{h}_{-ij})$

next i

if $(j < NL)$ then

compute transition equation $(\underline{U}_j \quad \underline{V}_j)$

$\underline{Q}_j := \underline{U}_j' \underline{V}_j$

$\underline{P}_j := \underline{P}_j + \underline{U}_j' \underline{U}_j$

endif

if $(j > 1)$ then

$\underline{P}_j := \underline{P}_j + \underline{V}_{j-1}' \underline{V}_{j-1} - \underline{K}_{j-1}' \underline{K}_{j-1}$

$(\underline{R}_j \quad \underline{s}_j \quad \underline{H}_j) := (\underline{R}_j \quad \underline{s}_j \quad \underline{H}_j) - \underline{K}_{j-1}' (\underline{R}_{j-1} \quad \underline{s}_{j-1} \quad \underline{H}_{j-1})$

endif

$(\underline{P}_j \quad \underline{R}_j \quad \underline{s}_j \quad \underline{H}_j) \xrightarrow{\text{Chol}} (\underline{C}_j \quad \underline{\tilde{R}}_j \quad \underline{\tilde{s}}_j \quad \underline{\tilde{H}}_j)$

if $(j < NL)$ then $\underline{K}_j := \underline{C}_j^{-T} \underline{Q}_j$

next j

loop through locals $j = NL$ to 1 step -1

if $(j < NL)$ then $\underline{\tilde{s}}_j := \underline{\tilde{s}}_j - \underline{K}_j \Delta \lambda_{j+1}$

$\Delta \lambda_j := \underline{C}_j^{-1} \underline{\tilde{s}}_j$

$\lambda_j := \lambda_j + \Delta \lambda_j$

next j

(continued on next page)

TABLE 3 (continued)

loop through locals j

 loop through nodes i

 loop through previous nodes i < i

$$\underline{D}_{-ii} := \underline{D}_{-ii} - \widetilde{H}'_{-ij} \widetilde{H}_{-ij}$$

 next i

$$\begin{aligned} (\underline{D}_{-ii} \quad \underline{E}_{-i} \quad \underline{e}_{-i}) &:= (\underline{D}_{-ii} \quad \underline{E}_{-i} \quad \underline{e}_{-i}) + \underline{Y}'_{-ij} (\underline{Y}_{-ij} \quad \underline{G}_{-ij} \quad \underline{h}_{-ij}) - \\ &\quad - \widetilde{H}'_{-ij} (\widetilde{H}_{-ij} \quad \widetilde{R}_{-j} \quad \underline{0}) \end{aligned}$$

$$(\underline{F} \quad \underline{f}) := (\underline{F} \quad \underline{f}) + \underline{G}'_{-ij} (\underline{G}_{-ij} \quad \underline{h}_{-ij})$$

 next i

$$\underline{F} := \underline{F} - \widetilde{R}'_{-j} \widetilde{R}_{-j}$$

next j

N.B.: $\underline{R}_{-j} = \underline{L} \underline{G}_{-j}$, $\underline{s}_{-j} = \underline{L} \underline{h}_{-j}$, $\underline{H}_{-ij} = \underline{L}'_{-ij} \underline{Y}_{-ij}$, $\underline{H}_{-j} = \underline{L} \underline{Y}_{-j}$

In particular, $\text{connx}(0) = \text{connx}(NL) = \text{false}$. We now only have to make the following substitutions in Table 3:

(j > 1) is replaced by [connx(j-1) = true] (38a)

(j < NL) is replaced by [connx(j) = true] (38b)

and the algorithm becomes independent of the number of transition equations introduced. The case of no transition equations is obtained by putting $\text{connx}(j) := \text{false}$ for all j, while the case in Table 3 (connexions at all interior breakpoints) results from $\text{connx}(j) := \text{true}$ for $1 \leq j \leq NL-1$.

5. Some Aspects of the Data Handling

5.1. Sparsity of Normals

While the submatrices $\underline{E}$ and $\underline{F}$ of the normals (19) and (29) are always full, the symmetric (NY*DY, NY*DY)-submatrix $\underline{D}$ may be sparse. From Tables 2 and 3 we can see that $\underline{D}_{1i} \neq 0$ iff (if and only if) both $\underline{H}_{1j}$ and $\underline{H}_{ij} \neq 0$ for some j. In the case of no transition equations, this is equivalent to saying that the nodes 1 and i occur together in some locus (j). In the terminology of the Set Solution, the objects 1 and i are observed together in some superframe; while in PRS terminology, the condition is that the two sets 1 and i have some Primary Reference Star in common.

When transition equations are included, the situation is rather different. From (ii) in Table 3 it is seen that a connexion is established between successive $\underline{H}_j \equiv (\underline{H}_{1j} \quad \underline{H}_{2j} \quad \dots \quad \underline{H}_{NYj})$ by means of the line

$$\text{if } [\text{connx}(j-1) = \text{true}] \text{ then } \underline{H}_j := \underline{H}_j - \underline{K}_{j-1}^! \underline{H}_{j-1} \quad (39)$$

It is useful to introduce the following concept. A chain is a sequence of connected loci, i.e.

$$\{j \mid j_1 \leq j \leq j_2 \text{ and } \text{connx}(j) = \text{true for } j_1 \leq j < j_2\} \quad (40)$$

If j_2 is the last locus in the chain [$\text{connx}(j_2) = \text{false}$], it is easily seen that $\underline{H}_{1j_2} \neq 0$ iff the node i occurs somewhere in the chain. Consequently, the chain now has the same importance as the locus, concerning the connectedness of the nodes. Seeing that the chains degenerate into single loci in the case of no transition equations, the following rule is completely general:

$$\underline{D}_{1i} \neq 0 \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad (\text{nodes 1 and i occur together in some chain}) \quad (41)$$

The submatrix $\underline{D}$ evidently becomes full if transition equations are inserted at every possible breakpoint (i.e. if all loci $j = 1$ to NL form a single chain). From the point of view of computation and data handling it is therefore desirable to make the chains as short as possible, while from an accuracy viewpoint, one would tend to make them as long as possible. For Dynamical Smoothing there is at least little point in connecting superframes on either sides of a jet firing, which sets an upper limit on the

mean chain length of the order of 500 s.

The sparsity of $\underline{D}$ may be quantified by the fill factor

$$f(\underline{D}) = \frac{\text{number of non-zero elements in } \underline{D}}{\text{dim}(\underline{D})^2} \quad (42)$$

This can usually be estimated by means of fairly simple considerations:

(a) For the Set Solution, the fill factor is the probability that two stars, randomly chosen out of a set, lie inside the same area on the sky swept by the FOVs during one chain or another. Taking into account the overlapping of such areas (factor ~ 2), we have roughly

$$\begin{aligned} f &\approx 2 \times \frac{\text{area swept by the two FOVs in time } T_{\text{chain}}}{\text{total area covered by set}} \\ &\approx 2 \times \frac{1.62 + 0.084375 T_{\text{chain}} \text{ deg}^2}{740 \text{ deg}^2} \\ &\approx 0.004 + 0.000228 T_{\text{chain}} \quad (T_{\text{chain}} \leq 1200 \text{ s}) \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

The lower limit ($f \approx 0.004$) is for the 'geometrical' solution with no DS, while for $T_{\text{chain}} = 500$ s we get an upper limit of $f \approx 0.12$.

(b) For the PRS Solution ('new' method), the fill factor equals the probability that two sets, chosen at random, have at least one PRS in common. If each set covers a fraction $S = (740 \text{ deg}^2)/(41253 \text{ deg}^2) = 0.018$ of the sky, the mean overlapping area of two random sets, assuming uniform distribution of scanning poles, is $S^2(41253 \text{ deg}^2) = 13.3 \text{ deg}^2$. This should be adjusted upwards to take into account the actual, non-uniform distribution of scanning poles (factor ~ 2 ?). Thus, if ρ_{PRS} is the density of Primary Reference Stars in deg^{-2} ,

$$f \approx 1 - \exp(-27 \rho_{\text{PRS}}) \quad (44)$$

With 1000 PRS ($\rho_{\text{PRS}} = 0.024 \text{ deg}^{-2}$), $f \approx 0.5$. Since we are now thinking of using many more PRS, the normals can simply be regarded as full.

With an envelope storage scheme (see 5.2 below), what matters is not really the fill factor, but the envelope factor obtained after a good re-ordering of the nodes:

$$e(\underline{D}) = \frac{\text{number of elements in the envelope of } \underline{D}}{\frac{1}{2} \dim(\underline{D})^2} \quad (45)$$

The envelope of $\underline{D}$ consists of the elements in each column from the first non-zero to the diagonal. Clearly $e \geq f$, but it seems to be very difficult to estimate e without actually setting up the connexion matrix and performing the reordering. For small f , it is reasonable to assume that e is at least several times f ($e \sim 10f$?). The required storage is of course proportional to e , and also the computing times for factorizing $\underline{D}$, solving, and backsolving, are approximately proportional to e .

It will be observed that the inclusion of transition equations radically changes the structure of the normals. If, for instance, one wants to "switch on" the transition equations only in the last few iterations of the Set Solution, this is formally made by putting $\text{connx}(j) := \text{true}$ at the relevant breakpoints. But this must then be followed by reordering of the nodes and the setting up of a new storage scheme for $\underline{D}$.

5.2. Processing of Blocked Normals

I assume that an envelope storage scheme is used for the (full or factorized) normals. That is, for each column, all elements from the first non-zero to the diagonal are stored. Several adjacent columns may be stored contiguously in a one-dimensional array (block), containing also a header with addresses to the different columns. The right-hand side is contained in a separate block.

When forming the normals, it is necessary to run through the observation equations once for each block in order to accumulate the elements in the relevant columns. This follows (in principle) Table 3, except with obvious modifications of the various loops due to the blocking. Clearly a lot of the calculations included on the first page of Table 3 need only be

done once, provided some intermediary data can be stored along with the observation equations for the subsequent runs. In particular, it seems rational to process first the block containing the right-hand side, while calculating and storing $\tilde{R}_j$ and $\tilde{H}_j$ (note the sparsity of the latter!), pre-adjusting λ , and accumulating e_i and f .

The block containing the left-hand sides are then processed in order of increasing column index. For each block, the input consists of Y_{ij} , G_{ij} , $\tilde{R}_j$, and $\tilde{H}_j$ for the different observations and loci. After all these have been run through, the block is completed and may either be stored (if the normals are to be saved) or immediately reduced (factorized) by the previous (reduced) blocks and by itself, and then stored. In the latter case, the block containing the right-hand side is reduced at last, and the system is ready for back-solving.

6. Conclusions

Two extensions (generalisations) of the 'geometric' set solution have been described:

(i) superframes, whereby the attitude around z is represented by a polynomial (degree $N-1$) stretching over several consecutive frames;

(ii) chains, formed by linking together successive superframes by means of transition equations (continuity conditions).

Let us assume, for the sake of reasoning, that a superframe would be about 100 s long, a chain about 500 s, and that quartic polynomials ($N = 5$) are used. One could argue that the chain concept is an unnecessary complication, since the superframe can in principle be made much longer by using polynomials of a higher degree. However, chained low-order polynomials (splines) are probably better for two reasons. Firstly, they should enable a more plausible representation provided that the breakpoints are placed at known discontinuities of the torque derivatives, so that the same representation accuracy can be reached with fewer free parameters per unit time. Secondly, using polynomials of degree 10 and higher might give stability problems (oscillating errors), not an unusual phenomenon when fitting to badly (or even regularly) spaced data points.

Regarding the accuracy of the abscissae, a very significant gain over the geometrical solution is expected when superframes are introduced. The additional improvement from chaining is much more uncertain, but probably less important. As for complexity, the only difference between the geometrical set solution and the processing of superframes is the dimension of the local vector, which is increased from 1 to N. This is a complication, but a minor one which anyway is needed for the PRS solution (Table 1). Chaining is a more serious complication, as can be seen in Table 3 [where the added lines are marked (i) - (iv)]. Concerning storage and computing time, finally, we can see that the fill factor, Eqn (43), increases from 0.004 for the geometrical solution to 0.03 for superframing and 0.12 for chaining. The corresponding increase in profile (envelope) will be less dramatic, but cannot be predicted here.

My recommendation is that the capability to process superframes should be implemented with the set solution and used in the final iteration (with improved attitude and ordinates), but that chaining is not considered for the time being.